

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of Far-Right Protest Observatory (FARPO) (2024): Protest Events by far-right collective actors (FARPE) (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.1, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/80D15888-70AB-4E9D-B7BA-BA632C85701E>

Abstract

The FARPE dataset lists protest events by prominent far-right collective actors using an actor-centered approach from 2008-2018. It currently covers 12 European countries, including Estonia, and will add more countries, including Georgia and Ukraine, in a later update (in the form of the Expanded CFP dataset) which is expected to be released in 2025 (1). The dataset was developed by a research team of the Far-Right Protest Observatory (FARPO) with Pietro Castelli Gattinara as project leader (3) and “seeks to ascertain whether, when and how the far-right engages in contentious politics.” (-Castelli Gattinara et al. 2024: 1). Of the 5.000+ total entries in this dataset, there are 91 events listed for Estonia. The data collection contains a link leading to the official Original FARPE dataset website from which both the dataset, the codebook and additional information are available as a free download.

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Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of Far-Right Protest Observatory (FARPO) (2024): Revolutionary Episodes Dataset (FARPE) (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/10CD51EF-08E2-4C84-B1D6-038AB13FCCC5>

Abstract

The FARPE dataset lists protest events by prominent far-right collective actors using an actor-centered approach from 2008-2018. It currently covers 12 European countries, including Estonia, and will add more countries, including Georgia and Ukraine, in a later update (in the form of the Expanded CFP dataset) which is expected to be released in 2025 (1). The dataset was developed by a research team of the Far-Right Protest Observatory (FARPO) with Pietro Castelli Gattinara as project leader (3) and “seeks to ascertain whether, when and how the far-right engages in contentious politics.” (-Castelli Gattinara et al. 2024: 1). Of the 5.000+ total entries in this dataset, there are 91 events listed for Estonia. The data collection contains a link leading to the official Original FARPE dataset website from which both the dataset, the codebook and additional information are available as a free download.

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Data Review – Revolutionary Episodes Dataset

The FARPE dataset lists protest events by prominent far-right collective actors using an actor-centered approach from 2008-2018. It currently covers 12 European countries, including Estonia, and will add more countries, including Georgia and Ukraine, in a later update (in the form of the Expanded CFP dataset) which is expected to be released in 2025 (1). The dataset was developed by a research team of the Far-Right Protest Observatory (FARPO) with Pietro Castelli Gattinara as project leader (3) and “seeks to ascertain whether, when and how the far-right engages in contentious politics.” (Castelli Gattinara et al. 2024: 1).

The unit of analysis within the dataset is the protest event. The research team defines a protest event as a “collective, public action, organised by a far-right actor (e.g. political party, social movement, group), with the explicit purpose of expressing critique or dissent, and/or advancing societal or political demands.” (Castelli Gattinara et al. 2024: 1).

The data was gathered via a keyword search for relevant news reports on both Factiva and Lexis-Nexis. The team decided to use only one quality newspaper per country to keep their sources as comparable as possible. So, they identified the main liberal outlet in each country to extract reports from. Tests have proven that even though that is the case, the reporting bias is marginal (Castelli Gattinara et al. 2021: 1-2). On top of the newspaper sources, protest events reported on official party/movement/group websites were also included (Castelli Gattinara et al. 2024: 1).

The coding process employed draws from the standard coding procedures of Protest Event Analysis (PEA) and follows three main steps. First the team undertook certain preliminary country-specific tasks. These include: (a) the translation of country-specific keywords (e.g. English: Name of actor AND protest; demonstrat; commemorat; gather; public assembly; verb accounting for marching; violence; occupation; action; rally; riot [Castelli Gattinara et al. 2024: 1]), (b) identifying country-specific events, which means listing all those events in which the far right is likely to mobilise, and (c) identifying sources, both newspapers and websites according to the above listed criteria (Castelli Gattinara et al. 2024: 1-2).

The second step is the coding of the newspaper articles that were identified as relevant using keyword searches, while the third step is to code the events identified through the official websites of far-right actors - including those already coded from newspaper sources using the same EVENTID number that was used for the newspaper coding. This is done since “one of the purposes of the study is to measure the difference in the way in which an event is described by the media (newspapers) and its promoters (the far right).” (Castelli Gattinara et al. 2024: 2-3).

The coded variables include: the country code, source, event ID, event date, URL, place, event level, name of the actor, type of actor, counter mobilisation, protest form, issue, and an event description (Castelli Gattinara et al. 2024: 4ff).

Apart from the raw data the Original FARPE dataset website also offers multiple interactive data visualizations including: (a) an interactive map of the yearly number of far-right protest events by FARPE actors, (b) an interactive map depicting the locations of far-right protest events, (c) a graph depicting the monthly number of protest events, and (d) a graph depicting the issue focus of far-right protest (1).

Sources:

- (1) FARPO. Original FARPE dataset. [Original FARPE dataset – Farpo](#). Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (2) Castelli Gattinara, Pietro, Andrea L. P. Pirro and Caterina Froio, 2024. Codebook for Protest Event Analysis Far-Right Protest in Europe (FARPE) Version 1.2. https://farpo.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/FARPE-codebook_1.2.pdf. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
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- (4) Castelli Gattinara, Pietro, Caterina Froio and Andrea Pirro. 2021. Documentation File: FARPE Original Dataset. https://farpo.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/FARPE-data-documentation_1.2.pdf. Last accessed 27.09.2024.